

An Assessment of the Contribution of E-Commerce on Banking Services Delivery in Nigeria.

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An Assessment of the Contribution of E-Commerce on Banking Services Delivery in Nigeria.

AN ASSESSMENT OF THE CONTRIBUTION E-COMMERCE ON BANKING SERVICES
DELIVERY IN NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

The paper focuses on the importance of e-commerce to the improvement of banking services in Nigeria.

e-commerce has contributed tremendously to the business by generating more revenue, provide more available information, increased productivity and generating new sales through new customers, and it also gives a company competitive advantage over it rivalries.

This paper has shown that e-commerce is effective and can be used as a strategy to meet organization objectives and goals. Organization should formulate good strategies to implement e-commerce into their structure and as the business environment, changes, organization must change with their environment.

INTRODUCTION

Modern communication and computer technology has resulted in the emergence of the new type of global competitiveness around the world in which a new era is fast evolving in information technology. The modern economy is becoming increasingly served under more secure competitive platform giving advantage only to those who have accessed and transferred from transacting business at a high speed to a higher speed and more technical method at a cost not contemplated a few years back.

The Global business community has changed rapidly overtime, growth and technology has not been separated and both have forced the focus on combining factors both to survive the era in the global market that business is been transacted daily.

Electronic commerce is a critical business imperative to global changes and most organizations, managers at all levels in different works of life now need the basic electronic information to transact business, no matter how less important the transaction may be. They are all looking at the Internet as a future means of defining the source of information they need.

Electronic transfer began soon after Samuel Morse sent his first telegraph message in 1844 and electronic commerce began in 1858, when telex message was sent across the sea containing the share price information from the New York Stock Market to Europe and North America.

By 1877, Western Union, the dominant telegraph company moved \$2,500,000.00 worth of transaction annually among business and consumers round the world.

Central Bank of Nigeria's stated that the Nigerian economy is largely cash based, about 80% of the total money in circulation in the economy is outside the banking industry. Alternative payment models that are technology driven are at infant stage providing only the basic functionalized services.

The need for this automated process brought about, first, the use of banking application software. This software helps the banks to collate individual and corporate accounts into one database. It also helps the banks in having exact records and helps them generate reports fro different purposes like financial statements, credit risk reports etc.

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Although banks were able to implement some automated processes, it was restricted to local branches. During this period one can only transact with the branch in which the account is domiciled.

The bank moved from automated banking to real time-online banking. This gave customers opportunity to make most of their transaction from any branches of their banks. These banks now have centralized or decentralized databases that make them perform these processes.

The introduction of telecommunications networks and the exploitation of software developers have given rise to different electronic banking products. Banks now spend millions of dollars investing in IT infrastructures ranging from Hardware purchase to software purchase, networking applications and telecommunication gadgets.

Nigerian banks have now developed different e-banking products, first to make their processes faster and to give customers the necessary convenience to bank anywhere and anytime.

The banks have also realized the need to keep aside a department not only responsible for maintenance of IT infrastructure but the development of e-banking, administered with the responsibility of developing e-banking products.

The introduction of different switches i.e a platform that helps all bank to interact via a web-based infrastructure such switches include: Interswitch, e-Tranzact, VISA, Card Center

These switches have also introduced varieties of products, which the banks can re-brand to suit their customers' needs.

The different products introduced include the use of Debit Card, which are magnetic stripe based, although some banks have moved from this technology to the chip based card: as found in many other developed countries. There has also been introduction of varieties of debit card: meeting different customer's need. Products ranging from normal ATM Cards to cash cards (e-wallets), children specialized cards, gift cards, credit cards and until recently prepaid cards.

Other products include Transaction Notification Services, Mobile Banking and Internet Banking.

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The consolidation in the Nigeria Banking system has also led to the fast growth in retail banking in Nigeria, which has also contributed, to the fast development of e-banking activities especially as regards the introduction of new banking products.

Electronic commerce transaction was licensed fully by electronic Data Interchange Commission in 1968, but it was not until 1984 that a standardized format known as ASCX 12 provided a dependable means to conduct electronic business and it was not until 1994 that Netscope introduced a browser programme whose graphical presentation significantly eased the use of computer communication for all kind of computer activities which up graded the e-commerce processes:

The meaning of the term electronic commerce (e-commerce) has changed over the last 40 years. Originally electronic commerce meant the facilitation of commerce transactions electronically, using technology such as Electronic Data Interchange (EDI) and Electronic Fund Transfer (EFT). They were both introduced in the late 1970s, allowing business to send commercial documents like purchase orders or invoices electronically. The growth and the acceptance of Credit Cards, Automated Teller Machines (ATM) and the Telephone Banking in the 1980s were also forms of e-commerce. From the 1990s onwards, e-commerce would additionally include enterprises Planning System (EPS) and Data Warehousing perhaps the earliest examples of many-to-many e-commerce facilities to come are the online information market place online consulting Internet sites.

What is e-commerce?

Preston (2000) defined e-commerce as any business transaction that takes place via digital process over the network. E-commerce is exactly analogous to doing business on the Internet. According to system audit and control association (SACS) 2002, E-commerce is the use of technology (telecommunication) networking to enhance the process of commercial transactions among companies, business partners, individuals etc.

It is important to know that the main requirement in e-commerce is the ability to accept a form of electronic payment, however e-commerce is really much more than just exchanging services or

product for money over the Internet. It is an enabling technology that allows business to increase in accuracy, effectiveness, and efficiency while business transactions are been transacted. Many business system still operating fundamental principles developed in the middle ages and towards the end of the industrial revolution, over the recent years have experienced a transformation of business and banking service delivery.

This transformation has brought about the development of computer based or computer oriented application to facilitate business processing system that will enable a better understanding, impacting knowledge and has given room to a new era of service delivery to customers. A new means of communication between the provider and the end user of the services.

The emergence of a secure, cost effective electronic payment system, e-commerce has become the sterling point in transacting electronic transactions. The Internet offers opportunities for both parties (service provider and consumer) to gain direct access without the attendance of physical presence to transact business. The electronic commerce medium competitors can emerge from anywhere in the world, they are not necessarily limited by their geographical locations. This has caused a fundamental change in the way business transaction are processed in the global economy and to service provider, therefore strategic implications for business become profound especially for retailers and financial services organizations.

Growth of e-commerce

Enca-ta (2003) reported that Internet has growth tremendously since its inception, doubling in size every nine to twelve months. In 1981, only 213 computers were connected to the Internet, by the year 2000, the number had growth to more than a hundred million people. The current number people using the Internet can only be estimated to be over six hundred million people.

The growth of ecommerce is at an incredible pace and the financial sector has taken their services to a new level, which puts competition into the growth of the sector. The application of e-banking, using computer to transact business has changed and switches the orientation of a banking customer to how flexible and easy it is to do business. The electronic banking application in Nigeria came in

lieu of the need by Nigerian banks to make their operational activities move away from the traditional paper based processes to automated processes.

Electronic Banking

It is not the quality of the information provided by e-commerce that makes the service delivery to be efficient, but the quality of the information and transaction benefits using the Internet that gives the uniqueness to the kind of service provided by the e-commerce.

The term "electronic banking" or "e-banking" covers both computer and telephone banking using computer through direct dial ups giving access to the internet or through telephone lines. Both computer and telephone banking involves the use of passwords which access to accounts. Using these methods, banking transactions can be transacted 24 hours a day. Computer banking provides access to account holders and allows the following via the internet:

- View transactions on their account
- Print out account statement.
- Transfer funds between accounts
- Make payment of utility bills.

Benefit of Banking

Offering banking products and services on the internet, the banking industry have been able to gain unique benefit such as:

New Customers:- anyone with an internet connection is a potential customer, millions of people around the world are already using the internet for transactions. This easy method of processing

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transactions have forced quite a few people to be influenced by the uniqueness of e-commerce and open relationships with the banking industry to transact business on their behalf.

Cost Effectiveness Delivery Channel:- Many products and services such as software or information can be distributed to customers via the internet, enhancing the customers experiences and increasing profitability by eliminating the shipping, queuing and other overhead cost associated with order fulfillments.

Streamlined Enrolment:- Paper based enrolment workflow is fought with delays: Applications for instance, a mortgage or a credit card processing details for instance can be help up in mails but receiving applications from the internet would be processed instantly.

Better Service Delivery:- Internet transactions have accommodated the detail in transfer services through electronic transfer services.

The potential of e-commerce is so great that no business can afford to ignore the opportunities it provides. The cost of ignoring e-commerce means that organizations won't be able to compete in changing global economy, they would be limited to information and other resources that competitors would have equipped their organization with.

Strategy Risk in E-commerce

As much as e-commerce is a tool to effectively growth the operations of financial institutions, their management team should understand the risk associated with e-commerce and evaluate these risks as it may affect their operations.

Prior to establishing e-commerce activities or services to it's various customers, a financial institution must have a structural and planned objectives it aims to achieve anticipating the cost implications and profit to be expected given the complex nature of converting manual processing of service to the electronic processes. Ultimately, adoptions of the electronic processes have to be done, but should avoid the risk of compromising the demand of their various customers. To achieve this, the financial institutions must put in place a structure that would become more customer friendly, employ the services of the best hands in the information technology (IT) industry, staff with creative

and innovative ideas. The meeting up to employing the best resources available would or may be the determination of the success of the financial institution.

Electronic Payments

Consumers are responsible for the accuracy of their own electronic payment instructions, depending on the payment instructions given; electronic payment instructions once sent may be final and irrevocable. So funds sent in error may not be possible to retrieve. It is the consumer responsibility to ensure the billing account and person payee information registered on the system is accurate at all time.

It is also the customer's responsibility to ensure that sufficient funds are available in the transacting account as at the effective time of the transaction. Payment processing would not commerce without sufficient funds. For standing instructions for example, prior to the set debit period of the transacting account, the customer must make available sufficient funds to the account in order for the billing process to complete the transactions.

Customers are to carefully and promptly examine their transaction to ensure that all transaction processed via electronic payment have been successfully carried out and a notification of the transactions has been sent electronically to them in with thirty days.

Issues Affecting the Development of E-Commerce in Nigeria

According to Census Bureau, e-commerce services transactions has increased in the sight years from 1999 to date by 48%, but is still in its infancy state. In the early nineties, a number of financial institutions had engaged in the use of e-commerce to transact business, but have failed (the distressed Societe Generale Bank on Nigeria aka SGBN for example was one of the first banks that introduce ATM to the Nigerian Banking Industry) basically because the technical know how was seriously missing. The financial institutions then, lack the technical knowledge to successfully operate electronic transactions then.

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According to Evans E.W (2000) some of the more practicable solutions that have been recommended as ways of moving the banking industry forward with regards to their communication problems and challenges are outlined below:

- Government should be sensitized about the need to formulate policies that would allow for long-term investments in the telecommunications industry.
- Emphasis should be placed on the importance of maintaining existing infrastructure and equipment;
- A reduction in import duties, tax and the time it takes IT equipment to be cleared at the customs is needed;
- The awareness of the banks, and indeed the general public, on the advantages of IT and communications should be increased by way of enlightenment campaigns and through any other productive means.

Another other issue is security. Security for the financial institutions and the customers in regards to online transaction is a major constrain. The financial intuitions have the responsibility to ensure that appropriate security control measures are in place to safe guide online transactions in their institutions.

These include establishing the appropriate authorizing access to transactions, adequate physical infrastructures to secure computer software and hardware alike. Updated data integrity of transactions and audit procedures.

Privacy is major issue particularly to the fact that financial institutions have a general responsibility to its customers and would project access into their financial transactions.

System downtimes:- These are a chronic feature of Nigeria's telecommunications infrastructure. While banks have WANS through which they can provide online, real-time service to their clients nationwide, they find that they cannot do so most of the time due to constant link failures from NITEL lines, which are often as a result of spikes and surges caused by PHCN inconsistent electric power supply. The reasons adduced by NITEL usually have to do with noisy carriers, damaged cables, damaged equipment and slow communication speeds.

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Lack of knowledge on how to develop e-transact systems internally. In all the banks, most of the systems in use were developed externally, or are off-the shelf banking applications. There is a need to turn the e-commerce department of the banks into proper computer departments by embarking upon the development of some of their systems in-house and training their e-commerce personnel.

Lack of e-commerce management knowledge: Just like most other companies or organizations in Africa, many Nigeria banks introduce e-commerce systems without proper feasibility studies which will specify requirements before embarking on a design. Codes are quickly bashed out and the completed system is introduced without any systematic unit or Integration testing of the code or system. Also, off-the-shelf e-commerce systems are purchased without prior specification of the requirements of specific banks where they will be used and usually without documented System Development Life-Cycle Model (SDLM). It is an acknowledged fact that most Nigerian banks have ad hoc processes. In other words, their processes are neither repeatable nor documented. They do not understand what is meant by metrics and how to design and collect metrics for management effectiveness. They also operate without knowledge or use of any in-house, national or international quality Standards such as ISO900-3 (Webb, 1993) and SET's Capability Maturity Model (Paulk et al, 1993). Much therefore, needs to be done in order to professionalize the e-commerce departments of virtually all the banks in Nigerian.

Lack of maintenance culture in Nigeria public networks. This has often led to frequent breakdowns in most of the equipment required for information exchange, with its attendant inefficiencies, in the banking sector.

Challenges

According to Evans E.W 2000) some of the major challenges facing Nigerian banks in their attempt to ensure a smooth exchange of electronic data and information are as follows:

- The need to build a better and more optimal infrastructure that will serve as a backbone for communications within the banks;

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- The need for banks to come together to collaborate in sourcing some new and common technologies such as the VSAT, and to decide common standards for credit and electronic wallet cards;
- The need to professionalize IT systems development, use and management in Nigeria banks;
- The need to impress upon the government and the public the importance of improving the present telecommunications infrastructure;
- The need to establish independent and private radio and satellite networks.

Having outlined the major communication problems and attendant challenges facing the banking industry in Nigeria, we now go on to look at ways to improve on the communication services being provided at a macro-level. These problems and ensuing challenges have been with us for a long time now. Plans are already in the works to implement all the outlined solutions. These will no doubt improve the present state of the public networks which constitute the spine of telecommunications in the banking industry in Nigeria.

Nigerian banks have now realized that banking today requires prompt delivery of services, efficiency and the ability of customers to be served in any of their branches in any part of the country, without any encumbrances. As a result of these, banks embarked on the use of integrated banking applications that can help them to provide efficient, comprehensive and nation-wide services to their customers through the use of WANs.

Conclusion

Computers and telecommunications systems have become very important as delivery systems and productivity tools of electronic data and information. Nigerian banks have now realized that banking today requires prompt delivery of services, efficiency and the ability of customers to be served in any of their branches in any part of the country, without any encumbrances. As a result of these, banks should embarked on the use of integrated banking applications that can help them to provide efficient, comprehensive and nation-wide services to their customers through the use of WANs. With the acquisition of the above systems, they sold their services with promises of delivering online, real-time services.

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However, they have been finding out that their systems are down for about 50% of the time. Therefore, the single most important problem hindering Nigerian banks from providing international class banking services is the poor state of the country's telecommunications infrastructure.

E-commerce made it easy to search for the availability of products services available in the banking industry, also e-commerce development has enhanced existing benefit by creating access to numerous resources and also, it serves as a major tool of change in business environment.

It has increased the productivity and also generated more revenue, creating a new customer and generating new sales and finally, e-commerce contribution to business activities through enhanced marketing.

The law and regulation governing electronic business / contract of sales in Nigeria should be made simple and not too technical to allow customers to be able to pay their money with ease; other alternative mode of payment such as smart card, value card, ATM debit card etc should be encouraged and developed by the government.

REFERENCES

- Adam J.S. 1963. Towards an understanding of Equity Abnormal and Social Psychology. Merlien/Psychology Press.
- Adamu S. O. & Johnson T.L. (1974) Statistic for beginners, Ibadan: Onibonoje Press (Nig.) Ltd.
- Baker. M. J. 1992. Marketing Strategy and Management, London: Macmillan Press Ltd.
- Ben A. 2002. Globalization_and International Trade: Implication for the National Economy, "The Institution of Chartered Accountants of Nigeria" (32nd ICAN Annual Conference) Nigeria and the Challenges of Globalization, Plenary Session Paper 1. London.
- Bell, D. 1974. The Coming of Post-Industrial Society. Heinemann,
- Forester, T. 1987. High-Tech Society. Basil Blackwell Oxford.
- Bill Gates 1996. The Road ahead, Pengium Group USA.
- Charles T. 2000. E-Commerce Strategies, Mapping your Organization's Success in today's competitive Market Place, Unilorin Libery, Ilorin, HF5548.32T. 74.
- CISA 2000. Information Student Audit and Control Association 2002.
- CISA Review Manual USA.
- Encarta 2003/2005. Macro Software, E-commerce Journal.
- Evans E. Wherem 2000) Information Technology in the Nigerian Banking Industry." Spectrum Books Limited"
- Frenzel, C.W. 1996. Management of Information Technology. Boyd & Fraser Publishing Company, Massachusetts, USA.
- Holloway, K.K. 1995. Using Computers to Branch Out, Bank Marketing, March, Pp. 57-62.
- Olufemi Babajide O. The Impact of e-commerce Transformation of Banking Service Delivery in Nigeria.
- Paulk, M.C. et al. 1993. Capability Maturity Model for Software Version 1.1, Technical Report, CMU/SEI-93-TR-24, SEI, Pennsylvania, USA
- Toffler, A. 1983. The Third Wave. William Collins, London.
- Preston G. 1996. How the Internet Works Macmillan Computer Publishing USA.
- Robbin W. 2002. "Auditor due care in E-Commerce" Information System control Journal, Vol. 5 pg 41-42.
- Toffler, A. 1990. Powershift. Bantam Books, New York.

An Assessment of the Contribution of E-Commerce on Banking Services Delivery in Nigeria.

Webb, P. 1993. The Application of ISO 9000 to Software Development. Proceedings of the International Conference on Software Quality, Lake Tahoe, Nevada, October 4-5.

Wherem, E.E. 1993. Information Technology in Africa: Challenges and Opportunities. ACTS Press, Nairobi; and RIKS, Netherlands.